

The Impact of Idea of Confiance Legitime on Knowledge Economy

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>In fact, the idea of Confiance Legitime aims to stabilize the legal positions of individuals and protect their acquired rights, because the idea is one of the most important foundations on which to build the state of law. The idea of Confiance Legitime also means the commitment of the public authorities to achieve stability and reassurance as a result of the actions of the country, otherwise it would lead to destabilizing this tranquility or storming this stability. The idea of Confiance Legitime is based on the quality and normality of the law, and the extent of its stability. Therefore, constitutional systems provide political and legal mechanisms to ensure the standardization and integrity of the law before its issuance, whether through committees or through its presentation to competent authorities because the integrity of the law before its issuance is a guarantee of the idea of Confiance Legitime, This matter would guarantee the rights of individuals and the state as well, as the individual can only obtain his legitimate rights in light of a legally stable system in all fields, as the existence of a kind of stability in legal relations, which sends the stability of legal centers, and works to spread peace and tranquility.</i></p>
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Introduction

Whereas the knowledge economy is based mainly on the use of qualified and highly skilled human resources, which play its role by employing those skills, knowledge and technology in providing distinguished and innovative products through which economic recovery can be marketed. Therefore, the concept of Confiance Legitime became the center of attention and centered around this idea a set of concepts that branched out from it, such as legal security, and stability of transactions, especially since the knowledge economy is based on an institutional system that provides incentives that encourage the use of knowledge in order to establish an effective innovative system for many parties, Under it, the legislator is obligated not to surprise individuals or destroy their Confiance Legitime. The notion of legitimate trust is part of the principle of legal security, which in turn forms the idea of the rule of law. These concepts would lead to stability.

The Confiance Legitime has also become a necessity in the state of law, given that the legal basis must be based on it; Because the meaning of the Confiance Legitime is the purpose of the law, a normative value, and its function is to secure the legal system from formal and objective legislative differences and defects of the legal texts.

All this necessitated the various legislations to enact texts that are clear in their rules and in their phrases, which requires avoiding the issuance of unstable legislations after observing the growing and widespread state of legal insecurity.

Therefore, the need for legitimate trust to maintain the stability of legal positions and support confidence in legal relations, in a way that prevents the image of the law from shaking in the eyes of those addressing it, in a way that helps to increase the speed of technical and scientific progress to maintain and develop economic growth in the long term, and until legitimate trust is achieved in A specific society, there must be rule of law, that is, that individuals and public authorities be subordinated to whatever role they play in establishing, approving and issuing the law, and that all their positive and negative actions take place within the circle and limits of the system and the legal structure of the state. Accordingly, we will deal with basic issues, the first will be related to the definition of the idea of Confiance Legitime, and the second will be devoted to obstacles to implementing the idea of Confiance Legitime.

Chapter 1

Introducing the Confiance Legitime

The idea of Confiance Legitime by individuals is one of the modern ideas in European laws. This idea is also a form of the legal security principle, which requires the necessity of the stability of legal systems in society.⁽¹⁾ The idea of Confiance Legitime or legitimate trust means that the abstract general rules issued by the legislative authority in the form of laws or issued by the executive authority in the form of administrative regulations, instructions or decisions must not be issued in a sudden and sudden way that collides with the Confiance Legitime of individuals; Because Confiance Legitime are one of the basic components of the standard of fair justice, and the basic goal of this concept is to protect the confidence that individuals have in the existing systems in the face of any legislative or administrative behavior that frustrates Confiance Legitime.

Therefore, we will deal with this topic as follows:

The first topic: the concept of the Confiance Legitime

It is natural that before stating the idea of Confiance Legitime, it is necessary to shed light on its definition in language and convention, and then explain the emergence of this idea, and then address the legal basis for this idea as follows:

The first requirement: Definition of Confiance Legitime

Confiance Legitime is a term of two words:

- Confiance
- Legitime

The expectation “**Confiance**” in the language in the sense of its root origin took place, and the expectation means in the language it looks at the matter, then it is said that it expected its coming and looked at it, and anticipated something and anticipated it, i.e. waiting for it and its fear.

As for the word “**Legitime**” in the language, it is from the initiation, and it is similar to the meaning of ease.

As for the idiomatic definition: the notion of Confiance Legitime means the country’s commitment not to surprise individuals with the laws or regulatory decisions it issues that contradict their Confiance Legitime and are based on objective foundations drawn from the existing regulations adopted by the country authorities. Others argue that legitimate trust or Confiance Legitime means protecting citizens from the direct impact of the amendment contained in administrative legal texts without prior notice by the current legal texts.

The idea of Confiance Legitime also means that legal rules should not be issued in a sudden way that collides with the results that individuals expect from behind their actions based on objective foundations derived from the legal rules and regulations in force.

In French legal jurisprudence, the idea of the principle of Confiance Legitime from the principles of public law expresses the idea that when a public authority causes a person to wait for some behavior, and that this expectation was based on justified or legitimate circumstances, that authority must take this expectation into consideration. When you change the behavior upon which this person based his expectation

In other words, if the management had previously taken a legal action with the person having an interest from this behavior, it expected that this behavior will continue, but the management has modified this behavior in a way that contradicts the expectation, then the stakeholder may demand the cancellation of the management’s last action, unless there is a sufficient or urgent cause for the common good.

Based on that, we can define Confiance Legitime as an idea that secures individuals to achieve their aspirations and goals based on their prior knowledge of what is legitimate and what is forbidden in the applicable law.

The second requirement: the emergence of the idea of Confiance Legitime

The truth is that the emergence of this idea came from German jurisprudence and judiciary after the Second World War, as an inevitable result of the state's growing interference in economic and social life, in light of a new outlook that normalizes the relationship between the state and the citizen that changed submission in cooperation and partnership based on trust and protection of trust.

The German legal system also defined the first translation of this principle in the Administrative Procedures Law. Then this idea moved on the European level, and that was in 1957, and it was the first time in the jurisprudence of the Court of Justice of the European Group, calling for preserving Confiance Legitime through the stability of legal centers.

After that the idea of Confiance Legitime or legitimate trust was classified as one of the principles of the European legal system, and was thus adopted in 1981 as a fundamental principle of the European Community.

Until today, the principle of Confiance Legitime has become part of the legal system of the European Community, and it is being generalized as it is an unwritten general principle of law⁽¹⁾ its violation arranges the

responsibility of the administration and obligates it to pay compensation, and this is what the European Court of Justice decided on May 14, 1975

The English judiciary also took the name of the *Confiance Legitime* (Principle the *Confiance Legitime*), with the diligence of the judge (*Deblock*), and the English courts took two disciplines to oblige the administration to respect *Confiance Legitime*, and the existence of a text requiring legal action

The French Council of State defined the principle of legitimate trust or *Confiance Legitime* in its report for the year 2006 that it is the principle of (imposes without prejudice to the trust established by those dealing with the administration in a legitimate and established legal status, by severely amending the rules of law). On the one hand, Professor Paraskevi Mouzouraki defined the principle that (a defense mechanism for the material right in the face of organizational changes and non-binding commitmen).

Therefore, this principle has developed and spread in different countries, especially in Spain, Portugal, the Netherlands, Belgium, the United Kingdom, and Finland, and in a famous ruling on December 8, 1994, the Administrative Court in Strasbourg made the protection of *Confiance Legitime* essential l .

The third requirement: the legal basis for the idea of Confiance Legitime

Some differed regarding the legal basis for the principle of *Confiance Legitime* or legitimate trust in several directions, some of them based on the principle of security stipulated in the Declaration of the Rights of Man and the Citizen in 1789, and it was referred to in Article Two of it and others believed that legitimate trust or *Confiance Legitime* It is considered one of the legal principles binding in the European Union, as the European Union obligated all members to apply this rule in all decisions and regulations issued by. There is also another side that believes that the basis of this principle is due to the principle of justice, and this principle is due to the rules of natural law, and the rules of natural law are the rules that are close to the human being so that they do not need to be stipulated in a law or constitutional text

While taking German jurisprudence in another direction as a basis for the idea of *Confiance Legitime* and considered this basis as the most likely and closest to defining the legal basis through these principles, which are legal security, the principle of the rule of law, and the principle of good faith, so we will talk about these principles as follows:

The first article: the principle of legal security

The principle of legal security or legal stability aims to stabilize the legal positions of individuals and protect their acquired rights. Because this principle is one of the most important foundations on which the building of the legal state is based, just as the idea of legal security means: the commitment of public authorities to achieve stability in legal transactions and to spread security and reassurance as a result of the actions of the state. Otherwise, it would lead to destabilizing this tranquility or storming this stability. The idea of *Confiance Legitime* is a modern idea of law, which European Union law has considered a general principle of federal law. This idea is a manifestation of legal security, which aims to stabilize legal systems in society, because *Confiance Legitime* or legitimate trust are a result of the principle of legal security, and that the relationship between the two is a relationship based on stability in the legal system, in order for individuals to act with confidence, and to preserve on the existing legal centers

However, some differed in determining the relationship between legal security and the notion of *Confiance Legitime*, and they believed that the philosophy of legal security is more comprehensive than the idea of *Confiance Legitime*. In other words, and clearer, the image of legitimate trust appears as one of the goals of legal security, because the idea of *Confiance Legitime* or legitimate trust is one of the basic principles and binding legal rules at the level of the European Union.

As some others argue, the principle of legal security has allowed the European Community to rely on it to establish rules related to the stability of the emerging behavior of rights, thus opposing the principle of retroactivity of laws and decisions, and calling for the respect of *Confiance Legitime* of administrative actions, while respecting legitimate trust is concerned in particular with the issue of the continuing impact of legal centers Arose in the past

The relationship between the legal security principle and the *Confiance Legitime* comes from the fact that the latter is binding on the first principle, and there are those who say that it is a form of it, and according to which the legislator is obligated not to surprise individuals or destroy their *Confiance Legitime*.

The idea of *Confiance Legitime* is branched from the principle of legal security, which in turn is the idea of the rule of law, as the European Union consecrates legal security and considers it an expression of the rule of law

In the information age, which the global economy has tended to implement the knowledge economy, the work to achieve economic growth is based on the possibilities of education and knowledge (human capital), which are considered one of the most important productive sources that achieve profits and benefits for individuals and companies in general, so a legal system based on legal security must be created. And taking, in

turn, constitutes a commitment by the ruling authority not to surprise individuals with legal rules that threaten legitimate trust between them, especially since human capital is the most important of these resources that are considered productive sources.

The second article: the state of law

There is no justice without law, based on the law and based on it, justice is achieved between individuals in society, because the law that must be associated and established with social life cannot achieve its desired goal without the presence of the body that assumes the task of imposing its rules in society, for the law is what regulates the behavior of individuals and their relationships in a harmonious way that removes the contradiction and disharmony between them.

Legal relationships are established between individuals among themselves, and individuals' relationships with authority are of great importance in providing the meaning of security, stability and respect for laws.

The essence of the rule of law is to protect individuals from the arbitrary behavior of public authorities, by clearly defining the rights of individuals and ensuring oversight of these rights. Therefore, the notion of Confidence Legitimate is a weakening of the rule of law.

As for the relationship between Confidence Legitimate and the rule of law, this relationship is consistent, being in a single delicacy, which is respect for individuals' rights and freedoms and not violating them.

Therefore, the goal of Confidence Legitimate is to preserve the confidence of individuals from sudden or sudden changes in the legal rules issued by the competent authorities, as this change would disturb the reassurance and storm the rights of individuals, and this is a basic requirement of the state of law, a prerequisite for ensuring the exercise of individual rights, a basic condition. To achieve any economic development or development, and a tool to provide legitimate confidence in the law as a basis for people's sovereignty in democratic systems.

The third article: the principle of good will

Professor (Chaumont) goes that the principle of good will accommodates the rule of "contract Shari'a of the contractors" whereby private law jurists consider that the basis of the idea of Confidence Legitimate is in the principle of good will, which the judge uses by maintaining the state of contractual balance.

The principle of good will is also one of the general principles of the law. Good will is considered to maintain trust or honesty in dealing, and it requires honesty and sincerity.

Therefore, some considered that protecting Confidence Legitimate based on the idea of good will in civil law is in fact inconsistent with the principle of protecting Confidence Legitimate based on good will, in which the application of the principle of good will in the framework of contractual relations was mentioned, and the truth is otherwise, the principle of protecting Confidence Legitimate that seeks - According to what is stable at the present time - to the protection of all those addressing the law from the sudden and inconsistent normative activity of the public authorities, in other words, the principle of good will is not specific in the field of contractual relations in relation to the protection of the Confidence Legitimate, but rather includes all law-addressees.

From this above, Sylvia Calmes says in her message about the principle of protecting Confidence Legitimate in the European Union and France, returning the basis of this principle - Confidence Legitimate - to the principle of good will, and considers the latter a condition for protecting legitimate trust, rather than its basis.

Based on that and after reviewing the legal foundations of the principle of Confidence Legitimate or legitimate trust, we find that all of them are consistent with the idea of Confidence Legitimate, but the basis or the true image of this idea is due to the principle of legal security, which jurisprudence considered a basic element of the principle of the rule of law. Because legal security basically means for the citizen the protection of his confidence, as both matters are the same in the end, and they affect one trick, which is protecting the legal positions of individuals and ensuring their rights.

The second topic: the basis for applying the idea of the Confidence Legitimate

There is no doubt that the idea of Confidence Legitimate or legitimate trust is the foundations on which these expectations are based, or certain conditions upon which this basis is built, so that the expectation is legitimate through some actions issued by the public authorities, and these foundations and conditions we will talk about in three axes and as follows:

The first article: the existence of an administrative act prior to the Confidence Legitimate

That is, that there is a behavior issued by an administrative authority in advance, which led to the individual obtaining a specific interest or a specific position, which creates an expectation for the individual with what it contains of future data, i.e. a base on which trust is established for the expectation to be legitimate, and if the expectation is based on information or convictions based on Facts that are outside the management's actions, or the hopes and wishes of the concerned person, that cannot be used to claim that a Confidence Legitimate

has occurred. Thus, the notion of Confidence Legitimate ensures that individuals achieve their aspirations and goals based on their prior knowledge of what is legitimate and what is forbidden in the applicable law.

Therefore, when the administrative judge protects the Confidence Legitimate, in this case he introduces the private interest that carries the expectations of individuals over the public interest. The English judge (Sedley) believes that when the judge protects the Confidence Legitimate or legitimate trust, he deviates from his reasonable approach, and that is in two matters, the first is when he searches for the reasonableness of trust and the extent of its legitimacy, and the second is when he is restricted to the public interest in front of this trust And legitimate hopes.

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If the legislator has the right to issue legal texts related to the public interest, then it is at the same time restricted to respecting the private interest of individuals. However, by doing so, he can nullify some legitimate behavior, and the matter may lead him to violate legal security, on the one hand must respect legitimacy, and on the other hand must Respect for acquired rights

Therefore, Confidence Legitimate are one of the basic components of the standard of fair and equitable treatment, and the main objective of this concept is to protect the confidence that individuals have in the existing systems in the face of any legislative or administrative behavior that frustrates Confidence Legitimate

It is evident from the foregoing that the notion of Confidence Legitimate or legitimate trust constitutes two basic concepts: On the one hand, the law must allow individuals to build expectations, which presupposes that its rules are distinguished by quality and quality, and on the other hand, this law must respect the Confidence Legitimate previously established by its drafters , Because Confidence Legitimate is what improves the essence of legal security, this idea requires certainty and confidence in the legal rules, as well as clarity and definition of the legal rules and decisions of public authorities, which means the availability of quality in these rules and decisions issued by public authorities.

The second article:Explicit violation of Confidence Legitimate

Among the necessities required by the legislator when laying down laws are maintaining the stability of legal positions, establishing confidence in legal relations, and being able to anticipate matters in advance and draw and plan future relationship. ⁴In the sense of respecting the Confidence Legitimate of individuals, which are based on the applicable legal rules and regulations, in a way that makes them reassured of the outcome of their actions and their actions with the related stability in relationships, it is unfair for the management to act in a manner that creates a Confidence Legitimate among individuals based on the clear and legitimate behavior of the administration Then the management proceeds to act contrary to that expectation without significant reason. ⁵This is an explicit violation of the Confidence Legitimate, which is one of the foundations for the application of this idea, because respect for legitimate trust has a constitutional value, so when the administration respects the Confidence Legitimate, it is guaranteed to gain the confidence of individuals who organize their situations according to what the administration sets in terms of organization, so respecting the principle of Confidence Legitimate or Legitimate trust enhances confidence in the administration and maintains the close relationship between it and individuals, so any action by the administration by focusing on the pre-anticipated administrative behavior, the expectation must be translated in the form of external behavior because the goal of the Confidence Legitimate idea is the commitment of the state to all its decisions and not violating Confidence Legitimate individuals, based on objective foundations drawn from the existing regulations adopted by the state authorities.

It is worth noting that the French Council of State ruled in its judgment in the Ste-KPMG case that the regulatory authorities must take the necessary transitional measures and provisions if the new rules they decided would violate or affect contractual centers in force and concluded in accordance with the law, in order to avoid sudden transfer And damaging existing rights, and the aforementioned French Council of State ruling established the principle of respecting the existing conditions, and the inadmissibility of issuing sudden legislative or administrative measures, and in order to achieve a breach of stable conditions in accordance with the old law, two elements were required:

- The first: is represented in the suddenness of the diamond change due to stability or due confidence.
- The second: is the imbalance between perceived interests, and the person concerned must prove the sudden interference with administrative behavior or textual amendments that have negatively affected his legal position in a way that he could not expect under the previous behavior of the legislator and the administration,because legitimate trust cannot be applied Except by taking into account the realistic

position of the concerned parties, especially with regard to their position, such as good faith and the pledges or obligations with which they were bound

The third article: the sudden act of management

The Confidence Legitime aims to protect the trust that is considered the right of those addressed by the legal rules and decisions issued by the state, and this confidence is represented in the stability - even for some time - for the centers that were formed based on these rules or those decisions¹⁾

However, sometimes the administration has a sudden action issued by it that is contrary to what the owner of the Confidence Legitime was waiting for, which takes the form of cancellation or amendment of a law or regulation or amendment in the provisions of the constitutional judiciary. All of these forms lead to a sudden and sudden behavior of individuals, and then leads to the violation of their legitimate rights, because the principle of legitimate trust sometimes takes the form of the principle of good faith that we have talked about, and it is supposed to take into account the behavior of the other party from the public authorities, and the principle of respecting legitimate trust. In fact, there is nothing but a "personal and realistic face" of the principle of legal security in the narrow sense, that is, the principle of legal stability that requires certainty and confidence in legal rules, as well as clarity and definition of legal rules and decisions of public authorities, which means quality in these rules and decisions. A manner that does not violate the expectations of those addressed.

The third topic :The link of the Confidence Legitimeidea with other concepts

There is no doubt that the idea of the Confidence Legitime or legitimate trust is related to other concepts that this idea is, part of and related to, in order for this idea to protect the expectations of individuals, it is necessary to fulfill these concepts, which are the main pillar of the Confidence Legitime, because the idea of the Confidence Legitime is part of the principle of security, which in turn is the idea of the rule of law, the link between the Confidence Legitime and these concepts would lead to stability. Given that the legal rule is based on it. Therefore, we will demonstrate these concepts that are related to the idea of the Confidence Legitime, as follows:

1. The idea of Confidence Legitime is linked to fairness and justice.
2. The link between the idea of Confidence Legitime and legal stability.
3. The idea of Confidence Legitime is linked to legislative justice.
- 4.

The first requirement :The idea of Confidence Legitimeis related to justice and fairness

There is no doubt that Equity is a set of principles and provisions that originated in England and were adopted in the United States of America to fill in deficiencies in the common law. Equity rules are applied by the Supreme Court and the Court of Appeal in Britain when the plaintiff cannot find a legitimate means to recover his right or to relieve the grievance.

There is also another term that is always associated with the term fairness, which is the term "justice", and the term justice is defined as neutrality in judging others, regardless of their ranks, taking into account the conditions of each person and the surrounding environment that prompted him to take an action. The term justice may have broader meanings, as it also indicates the correct distribution of resources among people, and other important meanings.

Justice in its general meaning (holistic) is the harmony and harmony between man and man and between man and himself, so justice in this vision is human justice.

Therefore, we find that the rules of fairness have begun to take root in the English judicial system, as it is one of the most important ethical concepts that govern legal relations between individuals. Justice and fairness require the existence of a set of rules that give decisions issued by the judiciary some flexibility, especially the administrative judiciary in which the judge has the powers Extensive in proving the abuse of the administration and its transgression of its legal actions and promises that created this kind of expectation, so it is judged in light of the requirements of the administrative dispute of a balance between the public interest and the interest of individuals and the dictates of the actions of reason and justice.

The notion of Confidence Legitime implies that natural justice or procedural justice is required of the administrative authority not only when issuing a decision that specifies individual rights, privileges or obligations, but every time the administration causes Confidence Legitime of the individual. The issue of achieving justice between individuals by the judiciary necessitates standing at the approach to achieving justice that relates to the application of the law and the interpretation of the law. In addition, achieving judicial justice requires the availability of a number of guarantees related to the judgment, culture, commitment and independence of the judge.

Among the applications of the judiciary, there is a case: "The plaintiffs rented an apartment in London at a rent of (2,500) pounds a year in 1940, and as a result of the circumstances of the Second World War, many of the apartments became empty of their residents, and consequently the plaintiffs rented the apartment rent to (1250) Pounds a year, at the end of World War II in 1945 and with the flats populating, the plaintiffs wrote in September to the tenants who were paying the low wages in order to pay the full rent for the last two quarters of 1945". Sufficient for them to pay the full rent, but for the rent during the war years demanded by the landlords, Judge Denning rejected the landlord's request, on the basis of the lessors' acceptance of the reduced rent and the tenants' reliance on that, fairness rules prohibiting the lessors from breaking their promises.

It is worth noting that justice and fairness have two basic forms, the first: it is not distributive through the legislative process itself, and the second: it is evaluative based on that satisfaction provided by the judicial authority to the affected in order to ward off an existing or potential aggression. Therefore, Confidence Legitimate are one of the criteria constituting justice and fairness, and the main goal of this concept is to protect the legitimate trust that individuals have in the existing system in the face of any legislative or administrative behavior that frustrates the Confidence Legitimate of individuals and limits the possibilities of sudden change of the legal rules issued by the existing system. Whether it is an annulment or amendment in the law, and it also does not violate the hopes that they have set for themselves based on the applicable legal rules, which ultimately leads to justice and fairness, because that is without doubt that it will be just and fair, and then meet the acceptance of those addressing him because it is part of the system of values that contribute to building the state of law and the legal base.

The second requirement :The notion of Confidence Legitimate relates to legal stability

In fact, the idea of legal stability means that the legal rules are affirmed, clear and specific in their organization of legal centers, and that they guarantee securing result (and this is the basis that the law seeks to achieve. The legal and decisions issued by the state, and this confidence is represented in the stability - even for some time - of the centers that were formed on the basis of these rules or those decisions

When we talk about the legal stability accompanying any community activity, or to achieve any meaning of security, this means that the legal centers resulting from human activity are clear, effective, and not subject to vibration and surprises.

The law expresses the needs of society, and it is by its nature in a state of development, but it is a well-known development, and therefore the legislator does not set up traps when amending the law or canceling a decision, nor does he issue laws with unexpected or sudden provisions, so legal stability does not only mean protecting centers The existing legal framework and respecting and guaranteeing the rights of individuals in the present and future, but legal stability also means respecting Confidence Legitimate and hopes with equal force, so legislation in all its types and forms requires a kind of stability and stability and moving away from the permanent amendment of legal texts.

As some see, including Professor (Fromont), in saying: "The principle of legal stability can take the form of a legal rule such as the principle of non-reaction, while the principle of legitimate trust sometimes takes the form of the principle of good faith, and it is supposed to take into account the behavior of the other party with the public authority.

Therefore, one of the characteristics and features of achieving stability is the rule of non-apology due to ignorance of the law, formality and legal evidence, the availability of the penalty element in the legal base and the validity of the judgment order, the characteristic of generality and abstraction in the legal base, the existence of a time lag between the forms of legislation and its enforcement, the completion of the rule of law and the principle of separation of powers, And the protection of the law against arbitrary change and the formulation of legal rules, all these characteristics and characteristics achieve legal stability for individuals.

There is no sense in the rule of law unless a sense of this stability is achieved among those addressing the law, given that the regulation of legal relations is one of the functions of law)

Based on that, we can say that the idea of Confidence Legitimate and its connection with legal stability is to exclude the risk of instability and the repercussions of a sudden change of the legal rule, and to respect the legitimate hopes of individuals from these changes. The threat and frustration of legitimate hopes is no less a violation of the idea of legal stability. Existing rights is an assault on legal stability

The third requirement: The link between the concept of Confidence Legitimate and legislative justice

Legislation has principles and principles that must be paid attention to when enacting laws, so whoever knew the entrances and exits of this art, was in control of containing the initial idea of the bill .

Therefore, legislation is the enactment of legal rules by a competent authority, and this authority or legislative institution is usually called . In other words, legislation is for the competent authority in the state to lay down general binding rules to regulate relations in society in accordance with established procedures .

Legislation should be comprehensive in a form written in an official document, so that it is clear and stable, which makes the legal rule specific, fixed and clear, in a way that negates ambiguity and ambiguity and

leaves no room for doubt about proving its existence or the date of its origin and determining the scope of its spatial and temporal validity with certainty.

In addition, the competent legislative authority should not issue legislation that contradicts the Confidence Legitimate of individuals, which causes them to lose confidence in the legislation issued, which leads to instability in their legal positions, breaches the principle of legal security, and breaks down legislative justice. Every legislation does not establish the goal of social organization, but is absurd, and laws that are not applicable or that carry within them provisions that contradict each other, or don't regulate urgent legal situations are blind laws (Blind Laws)

Therefore, it is imperative for the legislative authority to take transitional measures and procedures to ensure acceptance of the new legal provisions and not surprise them with them, and this is called the principle of gradualism in legislation. Legislative justice will always remain important in establishing social organizations, so it was imperative for legal systems to be more appropriate and safer. The idea of expectations has a great constitutional value, which requires governments to adapt various legal texts with the constitution, whose task is to balance freedom and power). In terms of legal security, the legislator is obligated not to interrupt individuals and destroy their Confidence Legitimate when enacting laws that must be objective and based on a clear policy based on the promises made by the authority.

Therefore, the idea of Confidence Legitimate requires certainty and confidence in the legal rules, as well as clarity and renewal of the legal rules and decisions of the public authority, which means quality in these rules and decisions.

There is no doubt that this alone guarantees the achievement of equality and justice among individuals, and it also guarantees the building of the legal state, so unless there is a link between the legal rules that make up the legal system of the state, so that they all fall into a hierarchical system that transcends each other, the state disintegrates and collapses Its legal system

It should be noted that the clarity of the legal text is one of the most important applications of the idea of Confidence Legitimate, as the legal text must be understandable and clear to all those addressing it. Perhaps the most important rules of clarity for the legal text are:

- Clarity of the general form of the legislative text.
- Stability of expression.
- Ensure that the words used in the draft law are the same as those used in the relevant laws⁷
- Avoid using confusing words.
- Ensure that the text used covers the whole meaning of this scope.

From this standpoint, it appears that there is a close connection between the rules of clarity and the principle of legal security, in which the notion of Confidence Legitimate is one of its forms, because legal security is a necessary characteristic to ensure respect for the trust shown by administrative rules and actions, because it is the expectations and trust of individuals, that is, they built their actions and actions with their confidence In these rules, it is therefore necessary to preserve the first, the stability of the legal rules, and most importantly the idea of legal security, of which the idea of Confidence Legitimate is part.

Chapter 2

Obstacles to implementing the concept of Confidence Legitimate

There are many obstacles that affect the implementation of the idea of Confidence Legitimate, which would destabilize this reassurance or storm this stability due to actions that come as a surprise or sudden actions issued by the judiciary, whether it is due to a shift in the provisions of the constitutional judiciary or through the interpretation of legal texts or in terms of reaction in Decisions and laws, which negatively affect the implementation of the idea of Confidence Legitimate, and then threaten the rights of individuals and their legal positions that they obtained in a previous law. Accordingly, we will address this topic as follows:

- The first topic: the impact of the transformation of constitutional judgments on the idea of Confidence Legitimate.
- The second topic: the effect of interpreting legal texts on the idea of Confidence Legitimate.
- The third topic: the backwardness of laws and their impact on implementing the idea of Confidence Legitimate.

The first topic: The impact of the transformation of constitutional judiciary provisions on the notion of Confidence Legitimate

There is no doubt that the idea of a transformation in constitutional judgments, whether by overseeing the constitutionality of laws or by interpreting the constitutional text, this idea is based on reality There is no specific definition, whether it is in the constitutional document or in the ordinary law, or even in the judiciary

Judicial transformation in its essence is tantamount to a change in judicial jurisprudence, so some people know the judicial transformation as: ((What was possible yesterday has become impossible today, or to say in general that what was acceptable will be impossible in the future)) The Egyptian jurisprudence also defined judicial transformation as: ((Abandonment of a principle decided by the Supreme Constitutional Court in some of its previous rulings))

As for the transformation or moderation in the French language, it corresponds to the word "revirement", and (Cornu) gives in the legal vocabulary three meanings for moderation, and these meanings are:

- The courts themselves give up a solution they were previously aware of.
- Adopting a solution contrary to those previously approved solutions.
- Relegation to a judicial direction

Based on that, we can say that the transformation in the provisions of the constitutional judiciary, that is, the reversal of this court from a constitutional principle that it had previously decided in its previous rulings, but there are obstacles standing in front of this principle - the idea of *Confiance Legitime* - because the idea of *Confiance Legitime* is one of the most commonly discussed concepts in Judicial jurisprudence, whether constitutional or administrative, may threaten the notion of *Confiance Legitime*, as the judicial transformation may affect the authority of previous rulings that the constitutional judge has diverted from. Therefore, we will deal with this topic as follows:

- The first requirement: the provisions of constitutional judicial transformation contradict the idea of *Confiance Legitime*.
- The second requirement: prejudice to stable legal centers during the constitutional judicial transition.
- The third requirement: disrupting the idea of legitimate anticipation.

The first requirement: The provisions of constitutional judicial transformation contradict the idea of *Confiance Legitime*

In fact, the notion of *Confiance Legitime* is one of the basic principles of law. Because, as some say, the reason for its existence The idea of *Confiance Legitime* is inconsistent with the fact that legal centers are subject to endless threat, and this source may be due to a judicial transition, and as long as the judicial transition requires a change in the law, this will contribute to the lack of legitimate trust, and then there is no consensus between the transformation Constitutional judicial and *Confiance Legitime* idea

Some believe that when a constitutional judge is presented to him a legal or statutory text contrary to the constitution, his role does not go beyond mere correspondence between the texts of the law or the list contrary to the constitution with the constitution under which that law or regulation exists, and the judge in this case is nothing but that he applies the higher rule (The Constitution), the shift in the constitutional judiciary in terms of its contradiction with the idea of the *Confiance Legitime* is that it reduces or weakens the sanctity and position of the constitutional judiciary among the public authorities, which leads the established constitutional authority to amend the constitution to restrict the role of the constitutional judiciary

Others believe that a shift in constitutional court rulings may be consistent with the idea of *Confiance Legitime*, and their argument in two matters:

- The first: That the constitutional judicial transition be limited and exceptional.
- The second: to be legitimate.

In terms of being exceptional, the constitutional judge should not overuse the judicial transition, otherwise it will lead to instability of legal centers. Because legal centers consist of a group of elements composed with each other, so that the legal status of all legal effects is produced

Hence, constitutional judicial transformation will be acceptable as long as it is limited in some issues and little, meaning that the principle is the lack of judicial transformation, and the exception is judicial transformation. Because the exception will contribute to the credibility of the constitutional judge vis-à-vis other institutions, because the means of judicial transformation is a technical means that helps the constitutional judge confirm the constitutional legitimacy.

The *Confiance Legitime* restricts the constitutional judge in his transformation of his rulings, and that it be few, limited and exceptional; Because the principle is for the decisions issued by the constitutional judge as a whole to be decisions that achieve stability and stability in legal positions and not to prejudice them in the event of a change in the provisions of the constitutional judiciary, meaning that the legal centers that have been established and settled or acquired by the individual should not be violated in any case

In terms of legality, the judicial transformation, since it contradicts the notion of *Confiance Legitime*, must be justified in a way that makes it acceptable and legitimate at the same time, so a shift cannot be accepted or described as legitimate if it harms, threatens, or freely disrupts Basic freedoms or at least increase their effectiveness

It is not acceptable for a constitutional judge to convert in previous rulings that reduce the protection of basic rights and freedoms, otherwise he is considered to have abandoned his legitimate reason for existence,

which is to protect the constitution, and in particular the defense of fundamental rights and freedoms. The application of the idea of constitutional judicial transformation must be in a specific and exceptional way so that the idea of Confidence Legitime and its actions do not threaten the future and not the past, so as not to threaten the authenticity of previous rulings.

The second requirement: Violating legal positions during the constitutional judicial transition

The principle in the law is that it applies with a direct effect on what occurs after its enforcement, and if the law applies to facts that have been established or to legal centers whose elements have been completed before the implementation of its provisions, then this law will have retroactive effect, for example: If legal centers are established in accordance with a specific legal text such as appointing or promoting an employee, then it was later proven that this shift contravenes the true will of the legislator, and the Supreme Constitutional Court issued its transformation, as this transformation is applied with immediate and direct effect and is not applied retroactively to legal centers that were created and stabilized from a date prior to the transformation in judicial rulings, and saying otherwise would destabilize the legal centers and waste the effects that resulted from them, and it is difficult and even impossible to correct this prejudice.

Therefore, the constitutions were keen to affirm this rule, making the principle that laws should not apply to the past. In order not to affect acquired rights, and respect for acquired rights, its roots extend to the depths of natural law and the basic principles of justice. Therefore, this rule must be applied even if it is not stipulated in constitutions.

If the constitutional judicial transformation has a direct effect, then this will avoid a reactionary obstacle to this transformation, and the judicial transformation over the future leads at the same time to complete the idea of Confidence Legitime of the law.

It should be noted that the French jurist (Mouly) was the first to adopt the idea of the direct effect of the constitutional judicial transformation, and the declarations were called warning or warning (declarations premonitoires) according to this method, the judge can enact a new rule in order to finally give a solution similar to the old solution, and from then, the constitutional judicial transformation does not have any results except in the future.

Based on that, we can say that the transformation of the constitutional judiciary has a direct effect and does not apply to the past. Because of its prejudice to the rights of individuals and their legal positions, and the demolition of their Confidence Legitime that they acquired at their time; Because the idea of Confidence Legitime, in fact, its legal rules are confirmed and defined in their organization of legal centers, and otherwise individuals lose their confidence in the law.

The third requirement :Disable the Confidence Legitime idea

The idea of Confidence Legitime is achieved by preserving the stability of legal positions and supporting confidence in legal relations, in a way that prevents the image of the law from shaking in the eyes of those addressing it. However, sometimes there are some obstacles or obstructions that affect the idea of Confidence Legitime, including a sudden change in legal texts or due to a judicial transformation, which leads to confusion in a certain legal system in a way that leads to a lack of legitimate trust. The obstacles that lead to disrupting the idea of Confidence Legitime can be limited to the following:

- Legislation inflation
- Lack of quality texts.
- Difficulty understanding the law.
- Violating the principle of equality before the law
- Frequent disputes.
- Retroactivity of laws.
- The excessive complexity of the legal rules.
- That the law does not contain standard rules, such as draft laws that only guarantee various requirements

These obstacles lead to disrupting the idea of Confidence Legitime, but to remove these obstacles, the public authorities in the state must play an important role in that, and the role of the legislative authority is to remove the obstacles, being the representative of the people who are the source of the authorities, and this removal is from Through:

- Eliminating the risk of instability resulting from the sudden act of enacting the legal rule, especially with regard to public freedoms, and that is by scrutinizing the laws that are presented by the government, and not rushing to ratify or cancel them.
- Ensuring the issuance of legislation in conformity with the Constitution, ensuring the protection of rights and freedoms from the negative and secondary effects that may result from the legislation through the issuance of laws.

- Work to build the state of law, to which all persons are subject to equality. All of these achieve legitimate confidence in individuals through the reassurance of their rights and legal positions.

As for the role of the executive authority in removing obstacles, it is by proposing laws that are presented to Parliament for approval, as proposals of laws issued by the government, known as draft laws, must be compatible with the principles of the constitution and respect the rights of individuals through the preparation of laws, and the laws must be clear. It is understandable to individuals and does not contain ambiguity in the wording, as there is an important role through monitoring the constitutionality of laws in removing obstacles that lead to disrupting the idea of Confidence Legitime, by respecting the articles and principles of the constitution, through political and judicial oversight; Because achieving justice in society will not be achieved through the legal rule unless it is properly applied in accordance with the purpose of its description and the legislative wisdom of its enactment, then resorting to the judiciary is a center of gravity in the balance of Confidence Legitime, because through the judiciary, the individual obtains judicial protection for the objective right decided upon Law .

Therefore, the primary role of the judiciary is to settle existing disputes through the application of the legal rule, if they are clear and easy, and if they are not, then - that is, the judiciary - is obligated to search for a solution by any available legal method, so the judge does not remain silent on the pretext that there is no text, otherwise it was considered a denial of justice, as the administrative and constitutional judiciary has an effective role in protecting the acquired rights of individuals, and it has a fundamental role in confronting the administration by obliging it to implement judicial decisions in all legal ways, and the administrative judge is obligated to cancel flawed decisions .

All these guarantees are a means of protecting and respecting the legitimate trust of individuals. Because legitimate trust is achieved when a person gains legitimate trust from the applicable legal rules, it must not collide with new legal rules that were not taken into account without taking transitional measures to not prejudice the Confidence Legitime

The second topic: The effect of interpreting legal texts on the notion of Confidence Legitime

The general trends in interpretation differ according to the different view of the origin and basis of the law , and the different views on the reality of the legislator's role in setting legal rules and the extent of the rules contained in the legislation . Therefore, he defined the interpretation as: ((Statement of the ruling applicable if it is not clear)). Interpretation is also an act attributed to an actor, which is the street in the law, the jurist in the jurisprudential, the judge in the judiciary, the scholar in the practical, and with regard to the law, jurisprudence, judiciary and knowledge based on metaphor

Therefore, the jurisprudence unanimously assumes that the interpretation of the constitution and the laws by the constitutional judiciary finds its basis in the position that the judiciary assumes and the specializations entrusted to him by the constitution and the law regulating it. It is unconstitutional and the interpretation process becomes necessary, especially when the wording of the texts is brief or vague . The judge's task is not to apply legal texts in an automatic way, but the judge plays a role in relation to these texts, by interpreting them to clarify their purpose and remove the ambiguity attached to them so that they can be applied A valid application .

Therefore, since the interpretation of legal texts that have raised a dispute over their application through the retroactive effect of laws, and this leads to the demolition of the idea of Confidence Legitime, applying legal texts retroactively to the facts prior to their issuance by criminalizing the permissible acts committed by individuals or nullifying their actions that have taken place As required by law; Because that would lead to individuals' lack of confidence in the law, generate anxiety in them, disturb stability, and develop a strong sense of legal insecurity .

Jurisprudence states that the retrospective effect of the interpretation decision does not constitute a violation of the constitutional rules or the recognized legal rules that justify the application of laws and decisions with immediate and direct effect from the date set for the entry into force of their provisions, that is, they are applied to the new facts that occur under them and do not extend to the facts that It occurred before these texts were prepared, as these rules and principles do not govern decisions of interpretation. Because these decisions do not create a new ruling or create a general rule that did not exist before its issuance, but rather decide and reveal an existing ruling that is applied and valid. However, is the Ruling considered a retrospective decision? Is the reactionary decision explained reactionary real or apparent? Does it threaten individuals' confidence? We will address all of this according to what some have argued, and the truth is there are directions:

- **The first trend:** believes that the interpretative decision is limited to just interpreting a decision or a text that already exists, and it entails certain legal centers. In their opinion, the interpretation decision is merely a completion and complement to the decision interpreted by the judge and its validity from the date of the first decision and does not contradict the principle of non-reaction), Hence, there is nothing that affects the legitimate trust of individuals.

- **The second trend:** The owners of this trend believe that the interpretive decision does not have an effect, as it merely removes the ambiguities and ambiguities surrounding the first decision¹

While some say² that the interpreted decision is an administrative decision that arranges effects that are effective from the date of the decision that came to interpret it, provided that the decision is explained by nature, as it does not contain in its content an amendment to the concept of the first decision.

We believe that this opinion is the closest to the truth. The reason for this is that the interpretation is required, as soon as the thing is clear, to remove ambiguity from the legal text, and in terms of its validity, so it takes place from the date of issuance of the decision, but there are some exceptions in the field of new laws or legal texts until they become retroactive, applicable to cases and centers arising under the laws Old issued in the past. These exceptions can be limited to the following:

1. The existence of logical reasons according to which the retrospective effect of the law or the text can be accepted without restriction. If the law is an interpretation of a previous legislation, then it is effective from the date of the latter's enforcement, and this law is applied retroactively; Because it is formed from the interpreted law alone, insofar as it interprets and clarifies it, or if the legislator explicitly and clearly states in any legislation for its retroactive application, and this reason is the other logical. Because the principle of non-retroactivity of law restricts the judge, not the legislator; Because the latter is the one who develops the legislation, he may appreciate the existence of a public interest that requires the application of the new legislation to the past
2. The legislator may explicitly stipulate that the law shall be applied retroactively, and the administration may also grant a license to issue administrative decisions with retroactive effect, which lends legitimacy to these decisions

Legislative texts in France and Egypt allowed the legislator to depart from the principle of non-reaction, with an explicit text³ Therefore, the legislator can issue legislation providing for retroactive effect as long as he obtained this license by a constitutional text, and the legislator as he is able to stipulate reaction in legislation, he is able to authorize the administration to stipulate reactionary in its decisions. For example, in France, several laws have been passed allowing the administration to take retroactive decisions, including the legislation issued on July 22, 1940 during World War II, where the legislator authorized the administration to take administrative decisions related to the withdrawal of nationality from those who acquired it from foreign nationals of the countries fighting against France, provided that The decree includes revoking citizenship as of its effective date

As for the jurist (Roubier), he went against these trends that we mentioned, as he considered that reaction in the interpreted decisions and laws is truly reactionary, as he considered that the interpretive decision has an effect. Because it removes at least the ambiguity and ambiguity surrounding the first decision, and based his opinion on the fact that there are administrative decisions that cannot be applied before their interpretation, and then the interpretation has an effect

We see that the judicial interpretation arranges effects that apply from the date of the decision that came to interpret it. The reason for this is that justice, logic, and stability in transactions and acquired rights are the justifications for the principle of non-reaction in laws and administrative decisions. However, it is agreed that no legal principle is devoid of exceptions, and the principle of reaction in laws and decisions is one of the principles on which exceptions have occurred. According to the judicial rulings made by the constitutional and administrative judiciary, where these exceptions constitute important legal principles.

The aim of the idea of Confidence Legitime is to restrict the retroactivity of some legal texts, especially at the stage of judicial interpretation, when most of the jurisprudence, when carrying out the process of interpretation, is bound by the retroactive effect. Because the retroactive effect would prejudice the legal positions in a way that exceeds the limits permitted by the constitutional principles, and although the constitution authorizes the legislator to determine the retroactive effect of non-criminal texts, but the constitutional judiciary restricts the retroactive effect of these legal texts, and they are based on a broad interpretation of some legal texts⁴.

Therefore, the constitutional judiciary has come to derive general principles from the texts of the constitution, which they apply to the case before it, and to subsequent lawsuits, as they are general constitutional principles, and examples of these principles are the Confidence Legitime or legitimate trust, which the constitutional judiciary in many countries has devised from the spirit of the constitution and the idea of Rights acquired through a draft law, and the necessity for legal centers to stabilize

Based on this, it can be said that the retrospective effect of the law or decision is to achieve a specific goal, and was designed to correct and develop the interpretation of the text in relation to the interpretive laws, motivated by a basic public interest, in the case of an explicit provision on reaction, so its use should not lead to deviating the course of the litigations existing before The various judicial authorities in the interest of one of the litigants, this deprives the other party of his right and affects the legitimate trust, and leads to instability and deterioration of the conditions of individuals, and then their legal positions are affected by rights and interests, and this threatens the legal security in society; Because those addressed by legal rules are averse to their application; It was contrary to what they were expecting.

The third topic: The retroactivity of laws and their effect on implementing the notion of Confidence Legitime

There is no doubt that jurisprudence and the judiciary unanimously agree that reaction is a dangerous matter that allows confusion and instability in previous legal situations and actions, meaning that the effect of legal rules on the past is not withdrawn, and that they are limited to the rule of facts that take place from the day they come into effect, so she pointed out many Constitutions, including the Iraqi Constitution of 2005 in Article (19), which states: ((Laws have no retroactive effect, unless otherwise stipulated, and this exception does not include taxes and fees laws)) Also, Article 225 of the 2014 Constitution of Egypt stipulates: ((the provisions of the laws shall only apply to what occurs from the date of their implementation, however, in other than criminal and tax matters, the law may stipulate otherwise with the approval of a two-thirds majority of the members of the Council. Representatives))

Therefore, the validity of legal acts, including the administrative decision, is for the future only, without prejudice to the previous actions and facts, when time passes it cannot return, and acceptance to other than that in the field of administrative decisions and any other legal action is a violation of the legal logic that must be respected By all public authorities of the state.

The administrative judiciary in France and Egypt also paid attention to this issue in many of its rulings until it was clearly established that the general rule is the prohibition of reaction in administrative decisions, whether organizational or individual as well¹

As some see that reactionary decisions arise when there is a legal center that has full-fledged elements in light of the previous legal situations, and this decision affects this position, either by amendment or cancellation.

Some expressed the rights protected by the principle of reaction under various names, so they argued that it protects the principle of equality before the law. In order to prevent the control and cruelty of reactionary law vis-à-vis some citizens against whom this law has been applied, and it protects the principle of separation of powers and protects the acquired rights of citizens, the wisdom of determining the rule of reaction in general, whether it is related to laws or administrative decisions, is the same, and the principle of non-retroactivity of decisions The administration did not come out of a vacuum, but rather it was needed, as it is a sure guarantee to protect the rights of individuals and satisfy the sound legal logic and achieve justice and stability in transactions

Therefore, to guarantee the notion of legitimate anticipation, the new legal rules must act with immediate effect. In order for the individuals addressed to it to be able to know it and adapt their behavior according to its requirements, in a manner that guarantees their rights and freedoms, and in response to considerations of justice, applying the legal rules retroactively to the facts prior to their issuance by criminalizing the permissible acts committed by individuals or nullifying their actions that were carried out according to the law; Because this would lead to individuals' lack of confidence in the law and instill anxiety in them, disturb stability and develop strong feelings without legal security.

Based on this, it can be argued that the retroactive application of the decision or law violates the idea of a legitimate expectation; Because the goal of legitimate trust is to achieve order in social life and in social relations, meaning that it achieves security, tranquility, and legal equality between individuals. Therefore, the principle of non-retroactivity of decisions and laws is one of the principles that the legislator has been keen to affirm and respect, and it has received support from the jurisprudence and the judiciary and approval of the public authorities. Accordingly, we will address this topic due to its importance as follows:

- The first requirement: The basis of reaction in laws.
- The second requirement: avoiding justice.
- The third requirement: the instability of transactions.

The first requirement: The basis of reaction in laws.

Reaction is considered a departure from the general rule that imposes non-reaction in administrative decisions and laws that are often identified in the body of the constitutional document, on the grounds that they produce their legal effects with immediate effect, and their effects do not apply retroactively to the past in application of the principle of legality, in order to preserve acquired rights, and from Then stability is achieved and legitimate trust is generated for individuals. For reaction is a dangerous issue in violation of justice, and this idea has met with strong opposition from the jurisprudence and the judiciary as a violation of sound legal rules and a violation of the rights of individuals, ¹ because the withdrawal of the legal rule on the past leads to a breach of the necessary stability of transactions and prejudice to the rights and legitimate centers that have been arranged under the existing law, and the creation of chaos and instability. Therefore, retroactivity raises great difficulties on the grounds that the administrative work will derive its effects in the past. The administrative judiciary has taken care of this issue, considering that legal actions will inevitably have their effects from a time

prior to their establishment¹), which led some to consider the retroactive effect to be a departure from the principle of legality and prejudice to the acquired rights of individuals, which may lead to instability and loss of legitimate confidence in legal situations¹

It should be noted that some jurisprudence believes that legal centers may be exposed to risks of instability even in cases in which the legal rules apply with immediate effect, without their validity diverted to the past, and his argument for this is based on two considerations: The first is to amend the rules Legal changes abruptly without being accompanied by transitional provisions, and thus lead to violating the notion of legitimate expectation. The second: It is the continued prosecution of the legal position, even if the legal rules applicable to this center have not been modified.

We believe that this matter is often excluded, and if it is implemented, then it is in specific cases, and the basis is non-reactionary, and then individuals who have touched their legal positions or destroyed their Confidence Legitimate can resort to the judiciary, whether it is the constitutional or administrative judiciary, to claim their rights set by them. Law and they acquired it legitimately.

The second requirement: Spared justice

Obviously, it is unfair to hold individuals accountable for past actions and facts. Because these people cannot predict or anticipate what the legislator may issue in the future¹), but it may be the opposite, that is, there will be behaviors that apply to individuals in the past, especially in the backwardness of administrative decisions, and the retroactive effect will violate individuals' acquired rights and destroy their Confidence Legitimate They achieved under a previous law.

Preserving the legal status is the acquired right that resulted from a certain legal action, and it is based on the principle of non-retroactivity of administrative decisions and non-retroactivity of legal texts, that is, it aims to protect a legal position that was born in the past and whose owner acquired legitimate rights¹). Because the principle of justice established by natural law is a self-evident matter and is required to preserve the stability of society and preserve rights and positions in it, otherwise it is a violation of justice and a violation of the rights of individual¹). Because the principle of the retroactivity of decisions and laws does not agree with the principle of justice, as it is not fair to hold accountable individuals who respected the old law and worked in its context and gained legal rights and positions under its provisions.

Otherwise, the rights of individuals and their Confidence Legitimate that they acquired under a previous law are destroyed, so that legal positions are preserved, laws and administrative decisions must not be retroactive to the past. Because the goal of justice is to equitable solutions, and it requires taking into account the subtleties of people's circumstances and interests and greatly dilutes the spirit of tyranny and exclusivity, and in this it means real or actual justice¹

The third requirement: Transactional instability

The public interest requires that individuals not lose confidence and confidence in the stability of their rights and their self-status that have been achieved as a result of applying the previous legal situations¹). Therefore, all legislations in all their forms require a kind of stability and stability and move away from the permanent amendment of legal texts, which affects the stability of conditions and acquired rights (Droit acquis les).

The reaction of laws is a violation of the rights of individuals and they lose their confidence in the law; Because the application of the law to the past leads to turmoil, instability and interference in transactions, by virtue of subordinating one relationship to two different rules. Therefore, Planiol said: "There will be no safety for individuals, if their personal rights can at any moment be affected, modified or eliminated due to a change in the management of the legislature"¹)

Therefore, the old should be left on its feet and the traces that were made in the past should be left intact. Because prejudice to it means the disturbance of people's conditions and the impossibility of stabilizing their conditions, the principle of non-reaction is a necessity for the stability of all transactions and providing reassurance by preserving legal positions and making them away from instability and turmoil¹)

As one of the jurists (Benjamin Constant) believes: reaction leads to instability in transactions, and it is considered an assault that can be committed by legislation, as it is a tearing apart of the social contract and nullification of the conditions under which the individual is subject to society because it is obedience, and (Digi) considered a violation of the law and that the rejection of legislation Backward legitimate command¹

The principle of non-retroactivity of laws and administrative decisions is based on practical considerations revolving around ensuring the stability of legal relations. This is because enabling the administration to issue decisions retroactively leads to wasting all safety and stability for those concerned in these decisions.

There is chaos and instability, as the organization is with respect to the future while leaving the traces that were made in the past intact, and this is why constitutions stipulate that laws apply to the future, and if the constitution does not stipulate the permissibility of reaction to the law, the law cannot be applied to the past

Conclusion

First: Respecting the legitimate trust of individuals is one of the most important legal foundations of the state through which individuals can be assured of their legal status and their acquired rights.

Second: Legal stability or legal security does not mean only the protection of existing legal centers and respect for individuals and their guarantees in the present and future, but stability also means, with equal force, respect for Confidence Legitimate and legitimate hopes. Violation of existing rights is an assault on legal stability, and the threat and frustration of legitimate hopes affects in a way. Great on the knowledge economy based on the product of human cadres

Third: The judiciary has a prominent role in protecting the legal positions of individuals and their acquired rights, whether through the constitutional judiciary or the administrative judiciary, through several principles on which the judiciary relies, including the principle of judicial independence, which directly contributes to protecting the rights of individuals, as through it everyone lives under human security Shamil is protected by the force of law, which no one dares to trespass on

Recommendations

The idea of Confidence Legitimate requires a sound atmosphere from the quality of preparing and editing the legal base to applying and implementing it as required. Therefore, the Confidence Legitimate must correspond to another need, which is to keep pace with the transformations presented by contemporary society, especially since the economy requires achieving comprehensive development through the employment of knowledge and technology in Providing distinguished products or services that can be marketed to achieve economic recovery, and this can only be done by providing all legal and policy frameworks with the aim of encouraging human cadres to be creative and innovative.

Based on that, all state institutions are required to support human cadres for the sake of economic renaissance, and this imposes on the executive authority several things to protect the knowledge economy and to surround the educational and educational institution with special legal protection as well as its observance of several principles:

1. Ensuring the principle of equalit
2. Clarity of legal rules
3. Stability of legal rules
4. Non-retroactivity of the law
5. Transparency
6. A fair trial
7. Avoid contradicting legal rules
8. Ensuring the rights of the defense

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